

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Characteristics of *Oryza indandamanica* Ellis, a newly discovered wild species

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A new wild species, *O. indandamanica* has been discovered in Rutland (11.50°N, 92.25°E), Andaman Islands, India. The perennial, herbaceous species was growing on a rocky slope over light loam soil, on a stream bank. Average annual rainfall is 3,000 mm, spread unevenly over 8 mo of the year. Temperature ranges from 27 to 32 °C, with 60-80% relative humidity.

O. indandamanica averages 10 tillers/plant with shoot fresh weight of 3.8 g and root fresh weight of 0.8 g. Basal internode diameter averages 1.2 cm. Leaf area per plant averages 0.24 m² and leaves respond to moisture stress by rolling. Unbranched panicles bear an average of 8 awnless spikelets, which shed pollen having 4-5% sterility. The grains are nonglutinous. This species is diploid with a chromosome number of 2n = 24. To determine the characteristics presented in the table, 10 plants were randomly selected from the original habitat.

O. indandamanica is morphologically similar to *Oryza meyeriana* (Zoll. & Mor.) Baill. var. *meyeriana* (Backer s.n.) and *Oryza meyeriana* var. *granulata* (Watt) Duistermaat with which this species should be compared. □

Morphoagronomic characteristics of *Oryza indandamanica* Ellis.

Character	Observation
Coleoptile length: mesocotyl length	2.59
Primary leaf length: mesocotyl length	8.59
Primary leaf length: coleoptile length	3.31
Leaves (no.) on main culm	4
Leaf thickness (cm)	0.0125
Length of flag leaf (cm)	4.53
Width of flag leaf (cm)	0.50
Tiller angle (°)	45
Average internode no.	7
Average internode length (cm)	5.36
Lemma and palea surface	Glabrous
Percent filled grains/panicle	75
Grain density (grains/cm)	1.98
Proteinous layer in grain	Peripheral (not uniform)
Scent	Nonscented

Taxonomic key for identifying the 22 species in the genus *Oryza*

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The IRGC is receiving more and more requests for seeds of wild species of

Oryza, from both rice scientists and biotech workers using rice as an experimental material. Recent revisions in the taxonomy and nomenclature of the 20 wild species and 2 cultigens (cultivated species) in the genus necessitate a revised taxonomic key to identify newly collected materials or to

reevaluate previous identification.

A working key prepared earlier has been revised and updated to assist biologists using the wild species as novel sources of resistance to diseases and insects and tolerance for eco-edaphic stresses.

A working key to the valid species of *Oryza* (modified after Roschevicz, 1931; Chatterjee, 1948; Tateoka, 1963; Bardenas and Chang, 1966; Tateoka, 1965; Sharma and Shastri, 1965; Ng et al., 1981).

- A-1 Sterile lemmas present
 - B-1 Sterile lemmas linear or linear lanceolate
 - C-1 Ligule of lower leaves 14-45 mm long, tips acute
 - D-1 Annual; leaf blades narrow; no rhizomes; spikelets persistent, 3-14 mm long, 2-5 mm wide; Asian origin; cultivated; diploid *sativa*
 - D-2 Annual; semi-erect to decumbent growth; without rhizomes; basal internodes spongy; spikelets oblong and deciduous; short anthers; Asian origin; diploid *nivara*
 - D-3 Annual, some perennial; erect to semi-erect growth; without rhizomes; tightly adpressed short secondary rachises resulting in more compact panicle; stiff, erect, ascending panicle branches; Australian origin; diploid *meridionalis*
 - E1 Perennial; erect habit; branched, spreading rhizomes; long anthers fill entire spikelet; elliptic pollen; African origin; diploid *longistaminata*
 - E2 Perennial; prostrate or floating habit; weak rhizomes; long anthers; adventitious roots and extravaginal branching at higher nodes; long internodes; lax panicles; long, slender, deciduous spikelets; Asian origin; diploid *rufipogon*
 - E3 Perennial; semierect habit; stoloniferous culms; long awns and long spikelets; American origin; diploid *glumaepatula*
 - C-2 Ligule of lower leaves shorter than 6 mm, tip round or truncate
 - D-4 Sterile lemmas almost equal in length and similar in structure to lemma and palea; ligule with a fringe of hairs at the apex; leaves broad; American origin; perennial; tetraploid *grandiglumis*
 - D-5 Sterile lemmas considerably shorter than the lemma and palea
 - E-4 Annual; plants erect; leaves glabrous to slightly scabrid; panicles more or less compact; lemma and palea perfectly or almost perfectly glabrous; sometimes hispid; spikelets usually awnless or short-awned; main panicle axis without secondary or tertiary branches; spikelet length between 7-9 mm; spikelet width 2.9-3.6 mm; tip of sterile lemmas acute; African origin; cultivated; diploid *glaberrima*
 - E5 Annual; plants erect to spreading panicles open, main axis with secondary or rarely tertiary branches; lemma and palea hispid; spikelets 7.8-11.0 mm long, 2.8-3.4 mm wide, always awned (10 cm or longer); awns bristled; sterile lemmas 2.1-5.0 mm long, acuminate at tip; African origin; diploid *barthii*^a